

Variscan recumbent folding of Ordovician plutons in the Malpica-Tui Unit (NW Iberia)

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The Malpica-Tui Unit is one of the basal units of the allochthonous complexes in Galicia (NW Spain). These units consist of a thick pile of terrigenous sediments intruded by basic and acid magmas of Ordovician age. Acid magmas are represented by calc-alkaline, alkaline and peralkaline orthogneisses, whereas basic magmas crop out mainly as meter-scale boudins intercalated in the metasediments and calc-alkaline felsic bodies, and in many instances represent strongly deformed dikes.

The basal units represent a fragment of the northern Gondwana margin having experienced Early to Middle Ordovician, rift-related plutonism, early Variscan subduction and subsequent exhumation during their emplacement over more internal parts of the continent. (FLOOR, 1966; ARENAS ET AL., 1986; RIBEIRO AND FLOOR, 1987; MARTÍNEZ CATALÁN ET AL., 1996; PIN ET AL., 1992).

The igneous bodies represent a competence contrast respect to the sedimentary host, that would make easy the nucleation and amplification of folds in them during each deformation event (subduction, exhumation and late folding). Structural analysis of Early Ordovician orthogneisses in the southern part of the unit has led to distinguish two generations of folds affecting previously flattened igneous bodies, as well as relicts of an original igneous morphology typical of extensional geodynamic contexts.

For the alkaline and peralkaline orthogneisses of Serra do Galiñeiro, to the south of the town of Vigo, the contacts show inflexions that can be interpreted as folds hinges in zones where a marked obliquity is observed between the contacts and the main tectonic foliation. The axes of large folds have been deduced from measured minor folds and from the intersection between the regional foliation and the contact surfaces of the orthogneisses or the sedimentary layering in the surrounding schists (DÍEZ FERNÁNDEZ ET AL., 2006).

Several down-plunge sections normal to the fold axis orientation (N35°E/17°NE) have been constructed and integrated. The result reveals the existence of a train of recumbent folds verging to the southeast, with an axial planar foliation refracted at their hinge zones. The recumbent folds were subsequently bent by open folds with vertical axial surfaces.

Analysing the cartographic patterns of biotite orthogneisses of the calc-alkaline group and their relationships with the axial planar foliation of the recumbent folds, hinge zones and limbs can be recognized for the first generation of folds (recumbent), and the interference pattern with the late open folds can be established. A mayor recumbent syncline has been recognized in the biotite orthogneisses, obtaining a cartographic evidence of a NE orientation for the axis of the recumbent folds, the same deduced from folds in the peralkaline orthogneisses.

Regularly-spaced serial cross sections normal to the axial direction of the recumbent folds have been constructed for the biotite orthogneisses. They depict a tight recumbent syncline, nucleated in an irregular, initially lenticular massif elongated in the N-S direction, which hosts in its hinge zone a semiannular body of peralkaline orthogneisses that draws what seems to be a recumbent anticline in the core of the syncline.

The apparent contradiction can be solved interpreting the semiannular body as a ring dike, which is in agreement with its peralkaline composition. Arcuate, oval, circular or polygonal shapes in plan view, with near vertical to steeply outward-dipping contacts and variable thicknesses and sizes (could be several kilometres) are the expected shapes for alkaline to peralkaline intrusions related with the volcano-plutonic magma plumbing systems in a crustal extensional environment (JOHNSON ET AL., 2002; COLE ET AL., 2005).

The syncline-hosted semiannular peralkaline body and tiny isolated peralkaline masses that discontinuously complete the ring are consequently interpreted as a ring dike cutting across an older biotite granitoid and its metasedimentary country rocks. This suggests an emplacement mechanism through near-vertical ring faults generated during collapse and fracturing of the roof above a magma chamber with a subsequent injection of magma (KRESTEN, 1980; JOHNSON ET AL., 2002). The ensemble was subsequently flattened and stretched during continental subduction in early Variscan times, affected by recumbent folds and bent in a late open synform.

Combining the alkaline to peralkaline magmatism and the structural evidence of rift tectonics presented here, our data support a geodynamic extensional context in the basal allochthonous units of NW Iberia during the Early to Middle Ordovician. Extension would have developed in the continental margin of northern Gondwana and was probably related to the opening of the Rheic Ocean.

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Pie de figura

Fig. 1. (a) Structural map showing D₂ and D₃ axial traces. (b) Serial cross-sections drawn normal to the mean D₂ fold axes. (c) Sketch with the correlation of D₂ hinge zones (thick dashed lines) that support a NE to NNE trend for D₂ recumbent folds. Fault displacements have been removed in the cross-sections to obtain the clearest vision possible of the ductile structures. Dashed lines in the sections indicate interpretation not constrained by the map. (d) and (e) Two 3D perspectives of the main massif of biotite orthogneiss

(BOG) made tracing a surface envelope joining the structurally correlated and regularly spaced cross-sections in (b).